

Effect of Entry Qualifications on Performance in Mathematics Education Program among Undergraduate Students of Ahmadu Bello University Zaria, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigates the Effect of Entry Qualifications on Performance among Undergraduate Mathematics Education Students of Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria. One objective, one research question and one null hypothesis were formulated to guide the study. An ex-post factor research design was adopted for the study, the population of the study consist of three hundred and forty-six (346) Undergraduate Mathematics Education students (309 Male and 37 Female) within 2019-2023 academic sessions in Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, the sample of seventy-two (72) students (65 Male and 7 Female) were selected using stratified random sampling technique, two instruments, student's confidential files (SCF) and semester examination question papers (SEQP) were employed for data collection. The validity of the instrument (SEQP) was calculated using Lawshe's Content Validity Ratio (CVR) and were found to be 0.60. The reliability of the instrument SEQP was tested using Cronbach's Alpha and found to be 0.84. The research question was answered using descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) while the null hypothesis was tested using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) at $P \leq 0.05$ level of significance. Research findings revealed a significant difference in students' performance with whom were admitted through NCE performing better than those admitted through UTME and ODE. Based on the findings, it was recommended that; students with NCE mode of entry should be given more consideration when selecting candidate for admission.

Keywords: Mathematics Education, Entry qualification, Performance,

Introduction

Mathematics is seen by the society as the foundation of scientific and technological knowledge, which is vital in the socio-economic development of a nation. One of the objectives of science education is to develop students' interest in science and technology as today's society depends largely on development in science and technology (Nigerian Education Research and Development Council, NERDC, 2007). It is therefore not surprising that mathematics is one of the core subjects taking note of a country's quest for rapid technological and scientific development (NPE, 2013). Looking at the importance of mathematics to human life and to scientific development in particular, effort has to be made to eradicate the learning difficulties of students in mathematics and hence improve the basic mathematics skills to be acquired at all levels of our education. Mathematics is the language used to express logical ideas, shapes, quantities, sizes, order, change and dynamics in the system and to explain the complexities of modern society in business, economic, academic, engineering and medical settings (Abdurrahman & Bolaji, 2018). Mathematics according to Alio & Anibueze, (2017) is the science of numbers, quantity and space. In other words, it is the systematic treatment of magnitude, relationships between figures and forms and relationship between quantities expressed symbolically.

Academic performance is the ultimate result of learning produced by both the student and the teacher as a result of the instructional activity (Sothan, 2019). In Nigeria, poor student performance has been blamed for ineffective teaching strategies and an unhelpful learning environment (Sunday, Olaoye & Audu, 2021). Researchers, educators, teachers, the government, and parents have all expressed concern about the factors that contribute to Nigerian students performing poorly in mathematics (Wonu & Zalmon, 2019). A lot of factor has been identified by researcher to be responsible for students' poor performance in mathematics and possible solutions were made but the problem remain unchanged. Despite all these factors experts believed that, the performance should be used as a yard-stick for promotion, award of certificate and appointment (Sadauki, 2015). This observation became a challenge and this is why the present study has been raised to verify if entry qualifications may help in resolving this trend.

As it may apply to academic life, previous performances may be assessed to determine elements that are contributory to continuous performance on educational and career paths and therefore can be predicted to assure continuous improvement. The need to correlate entry qualification and performance of undergraduate students has been appreciated by many psychologists. The selection of right candidates for the university education is as important as the quality of instruction. Academic success is no doubt the main focus of all educational programmes and thus received tremendous attention from educators. However, predicting academic performance through entry qualification is not yet clear. Over the years, there have been concerns about the correlation between the pre-admission qualification of students and their academic performance in the university. This appears to be a global source of concern in view of the ongoing debates and studies on the issue in different countries (Farooq & Mlambo, 2011).

The academic performance of students admitted in to universities has been an issue of great concern to many educationists in Nigeria and the whole world. The decay in the educational system calls for attention and hence the search for the most desirable mode of selecting candidates for admission into Nigerian universities continues unabated.

Despite the vital roles played by mathematics in scientific and technological development of the whole nation, its teaching and learning are faced with some problems that make most students to perform poorly in the subject which might have resulted from different factors among them entry qualification may be one (Tanimu, 2019). Also, the non-uniformity in the three modes of entry; UTME, ODE and NCE is another issue of concern, yet are all considered to have the same experience during class room instructions and examinations. This observation became a challenge and this is why the current effort is being embarked upon to verify the claim. Bratti and Staffolani (2006) observed that the measurement of the students' prior educational outcomes or performance is the most important indicator or determinant of the students' future academic performance. This is because the quality of any programme is estimated among other things on the qualifications at the entrant.

Objective of the Study

The purpose of this study was to compare the 'Effects of Entry Qualification among Undergraduate Mathematics Education Students of Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria'. The study aimed to determine the differences among the three entry qualifications that may lead to a desired performance of the students at the end of 200 level. Specifically, the study aimed to;

1. Determine the effects of the three modes of admission on Performance among Undergraduate Mathematics Education Students of Ahmadu Bello University Zaria.

Research Question

The following research question was raised to guide the conduct of the study;

1. Is there any significant difference among the effects of the three modes of admission on performance among undergraduate Mathematics Education Students of Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria?

Hypothesis

The following null hypothesis were formulated and tested at 0.05 significant level;

1. H_{01} : There is no significant difference between the three modes of admission on performance among Undergraduate Mathematics Education Students of Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria.

Research Design

The research design used was an ex-post factor research design otherwise known as causal-comparative research design. This research design attempts to explore cause and effects relationship where causes already exist and cannot be manipulated. Simon (2013) suggested that ex-post factor research design is ideal for conducting social research when it is not possible or acceptable to manipulate the characteristics of human participant.

Population of the Study

The population of this study consisted of all undergraduate mathematics education students of A.B.U, Zaria from 2019 – 2023 academic session. The available population were three hundred and forty-six (346) students, among them fifty-six (56) students were from 400 level i.e 2019/2020 academic session, seventy-five (75) students were from 300 level i.e 2020/2021 academic session, seventy-nine (79) students were from 200 level i.e 2021/2022 academic session and one hundred and thirty-six (136) students were from 100 level i.e 2022/2023 academic session, as presented in Table 1;

Table 1: Population of the Study

S/N	Level	Entry qualification	No of Students		Total
			Male	Female	
1.	400 Level				
i.		UTME	05	-	05
ii.		ODE	16	3	19
iii.		NCE	24	-	24
iv.	HND	8	-	08	
2.	300 Level				
i.		UTME	30	5	35
ii.		ODE	12	3	15
iii.		NCE	13	1	14
iv.	HND	10	1	11	
3.	200 Level				
i.		UTME	17	2	19
ii.		ODE	18	1	19
iii.	NCE	37	4	41	
4.	100 Level				
i.	UTME	119	17	136	
Total			309	37	346

Source: Science Education Exams office (2023)

Sample and Sampling Technique

The sample for the study comprises of 200 level undergraduate mathematics education students of A.B.U, Zaria of 2021/2022 academic sessions. The available sample were seventy-two (72) students among them sixty-five (65) students were male and seven (7) students were female. The choice of selecting 200 level is because it is at 200 level candidates admitted through DE are gathered together with those admitted through UTME and proceed with same training with the expectation performing equally well. It is also assumed that at this level, candidates depend purely on their entry qualifications before adjusting to other experiences influence by the academic environment. Stratified sampling technique was used to select the sample. The samples were divided into three (3) strata based on the three entry qualifications UTME, OND and NCE. The researcher takes each of the entry qualification as strata for easy categorization and selection of the sample as presented in Table 2;

Table 2 Sample for the Study

S/N	Entry qualification	No of Students		Total
		Male	Female	
1.	UTME	16	2	18
2.	ODE	13	1	14
3.	NCE	36	4	40
Total		65	7	72

Instrumentation

The instruments used for data collection were documents (student’s confidential files, SCF), collected in an official manner and two semesters examination question papers (SEQP) for 2021 – 2022 academic session, some of the question papers were collected from the various departments’ examinations offices while some from the faculty library. Students’ bio-data were collected from their confidential files at Mathematics Education Section, Department of Science Education, Faculty of Education A.B.U, Zaria.

Validation of the Instrument

SEQP were validated by seven experts whose ranks are ranging from Senior lecturer and above from department of Mathematics and Science Education where the examinations were set up after which the researcher used Lawshe’s Content Validity Ratio (CVR) to determine the average validity ratio and found the average validity ratio to be 0.60 which implies that the instrument is valid.

Method of Data Collection

Results of the students (CGPA) at the end of two hundred level (200 level) were collected from the examination office of the department of science education, faculty of education ABU, Zaria, by the approval of the H.O.D. CGPA of seventy-two (72) students were collected with eighteen (18) students from UTME mode of admission, fourteen (14) students from ODE mode of admission and forty (40) students from NCE mode of admission. Data were sorted based on entry qualification.

Result

Research Question

1. Is there any significant difference among the effects of the three modes of admission on performance among Undergraduate Mathematics Education Students of Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria?

These research questions were summarized in Table 3 using descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation)

Table 3: Descriptive statistics for the performance of undergraduate mathematic education students with different entry qualifications.

Entry Qualification	N	Mean CGPA	Std. Deviation
UTME	18	1.80	1.05
ODE	14	1.86	1.14
NCE	40	2.16	1.11

Table 3 shows the mean CGPA for the performance of 2020/2021 students admitted through UTME as; 1.80, those admitted through ODE as; 1.86 and those admitted through NCE as; 2.16 with their respective standard deviations as; 1.05, 1.14 and 1.11.

Hypothesis

H₀:

There is no significant difference between the three modes of entry qualifications on performance among Undergraduate Mathematics Education Students of Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria.

The null hypothesis was tested in Table 4 using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) at 0.05 level of significance.

Table 4: One-way ANOVA for the performance of undergraduate mathematics education students with different entry qualifications.

Groups	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	F-ratio	P-value
Between Groups	13.20	2	6.60		
Within Groups	73.49	69	1.07	6.20	0.03
Total	86.69	71			

Decision Criterion: Reject H₀ if P-value ≤ 0.05

Table 4 shows a P-value of 0.03 between and within the three groups which was less than 0.05, therefore H₀ which state that; there is no significant difference between the three modes of entry qualifications on performance among Undergraduate Mathematics Education Students of Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria was rejected. This indicates that there was a significant difference among the effect of the three entry qualifications on performance among mathematics education students of A. B. U, Zaria. This difference was shown in the Post Hoc Table 5;

Table 5: Post Hoc Test showing the difference in performance of undergraduate mathematics education students with different entry qualifications.

(I) Entry Qualification	(J) Entry Qualification	Mean Difference (I-J)	P-value
UTME	ODE	-0.06	0.99
	NCE	-0.89	0.01
ODE	UTME	0.06	0.99
	NCE	-0.83	0.03

NCE	UTME	0.89	0.01
	ODE	0.83	0.03

From Table 5, it can be observed that, the P-value between students admitted through UTME and those admitted through NCE was 0.01, this indicates that significant difference exists between the performance of the students admitted through the two modes of entry (UTME and NCE). At the same time, the Table shows a P-value of 0.03 between the performance of students admitted through ODE and those admitted through NCE which also indicates that there exists a significant difference between the performance of the students admitted through the two modes of entry (ODE and NCE).

Discussion of Findings

Table 4, shows a p-value of 0.03 between and within the three groups which was less than 0.05, therefore H_0 which states that; there is no significant difference among the effects of the three entry qualifications on performance among undergraduate mathematics education students of A. B. U, Zaria was rejected. This indicates that; there exists a significant difference among the effect of the three entry qualifications on performance of mathematics education students of A. B. U, Zaria. This difference was shown in the Post Hoc Table 5, indicated a P- value of 0.01 between students admitted through UTME and those admitted through NCE. The Table also shows a P-value of 0.03 between the performance of students admitted through ODE and those admitted through NCE. This indicates that students admitted through NCE perform better since the Table shows a P-value of 0.99 between the performances of students admitted through ODE and those admitted through UTME. This clearly indicates that the poor performance arises from the ODE mode of entry. This finding contradicts all other findings from the literature reviewed. It also shows that; there are other factors that affect the performance of the students and not necessarily as a result of mode of entry. Thus, these factors may need to be investigated by other researchers.

Conclusions

Based on the findings from this study, the researcher concluded that there was a significant difference among the effects of the three modes of admission, it was observed that students admitted through NCE were the high-performance group among the three entry qualifications followed by those students admitted through UTME, the students admitted through ODE were found to perform slightly lower among the three modes of admissions. This clearly indicates that the performance of students in university education depends on the experiences of students under the influence of the university instructional environment. However, the findings suggest that students admitted through ODE and those admitted through UTME modes of admissions need monitoring and mentoring to ensure better academic performance. The implication of this study therefore is that students' performance is largely a function of the number of efforts put into study among other factors and not necessarily as a result of mode of entry into the university. The findings suggest the need to consider NCE modes of admissions as the most appropriate criteria for selecting prospective students into undergraduate mathematics education programme in Nigerian universities.

Recommendations

Based on the findings generated from this study, the following recommendations were made

1. A special orientation program should be organized to all new undergraduate mathematics education students especially those admitted through ODE and UTME to help them adapt to the university learning environment. This program can include study skills orientation, independent learning, understanding the semester system and how to easily capture the mathematics concepts. This will equip students to cope with the academic rigors of mathematic study.
2. Academicians teaching mathematics courses need to be made aware that students enrolling into the program at two hundred level (200level) have different background and experiences so they need special attention to enable all the students in the class to benefit from the class room instruction which may help to improve their performance. They should also be given proper training in planning and teaching a course with variation of student backgrounds.
3. It was also recommended that the department may need to conduct oral screening exercise as a means of further screening of prospective students in order to have the opportunity of interacting with them personally to elicit those who were able to justify their entry qualification.

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